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ACCIDENT AT WORK: TYPES AND PROCEDURE FOR INVESTIGATION

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ABSTRACT

The procedure for investigating and recording industrial accidents is regulated at the legislative level of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Despite this, accidents at work and occupational diseases remain a serious problem and cause significant economic losses. In order to minimize this problem, the relevant authorities must necessarily keep a record of all accidents at work, as well as hold the perpetrators accountable in order to prevent and alert the occurrence of accidents at work in the future.

Keywords: accident at work, victim, employee, employer, occupational disease, degree of loss of professional ability to work, work injury, contract of compulsory insurance of civil liability of the employer.

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НЕСЧАСТНЫЙ СЛУЧАЙ НА ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕ: ВИДЫ И ПОРЯДОК РАССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В Республике Узбекистан на законодательном уровне регламентирован порядок расследования и учета несчастных случаев на производстве. Несмотря на это несчастные случаи на производстве и профессиональные заболевания остаются серьезной проблемой и причиной существенных экономических потерь. Чтобы минимизировать эту проблему соответствующие органы должны обязательно вести учет всех несчастных случаев на производстве, а также привлекать к ответственности виновных лиц в целях предотвращения и предупреждения в будущем возникновения несчастных случаев на производстве.

Ключевые слова: несчастный случай на производстве, потерпевший, работник, работодатель, профессиональное заболевание, степень утраты профессиональной трудоспособности, трудовое увечье, договор обязательного страхования гражданской ответственности работодателя.

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ISHDAGI BAXTSIZ HODISALAR: TERGOV TURLARI VA TARTIBI**ANNOTATSIYA**

O‘zbekiston Respublikasida ishlab chiqarishdagi baxtsiz hodisalarni tekshirish va hisobga olish tartibi qonunchilik darajasida tartibga solinadi. Shunga qaramay, ishlab chiqarishdagi baxtsiz hodisalar va kasb kasalliklari jiddiy muammo bo‘lib qolmoqda va katta iqtisodiy yo‘qotishlarga olib keladi. Ushbu muammoni minimallashtirish uchun tegishli organlar ishlab chiqarishdagi barcha baxtsiz hodisalarni majburiy ravishda hisobga olishlari, shuningdek, kelajakda ishlab chiqarishdagi baxtsiz hodisalarni hisobga olish va oldini olish uchun aybdorlarni javobgarlikka tortishlari kerak.

Kalit so‘zlar: ishlab chiqarishdagi baxtsiz hodisa, jabrlanuvchi, xodim, ish beruvchi, kasb kasalligi, kasbiy mehnat qobiliyatini yo‘qotish darajasi, mehnat jarohati, ish beruvchining fuqarolik javobgarligini majburiy sug‘urta qilish shartnomasi.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the problems of ensuring safe working conditions, preventing industrial accidents, occupational diseases, reducing occupational morbidity and, accordingly, the associated economic losses remain quite acute. Thus, the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes the need to investigate and record industrial accidents and occupational diseases in order to protect the legitimate interests of workers affected by industrial accidents and occupational diseases (family members of the deceased), to identify persons guilty of violating the protection requirement labor, as well as the development of measures to eliminate the causes of industrial injuries.

Absolutely every employer is faced with the issue of employee safety. The employer is obliged to take measures related to the preservation of his life and health during the entire labor activity. Despite all the measures taken, in practice there are injuries at the production facility, including cases with a fatal outcome. The number of diseases associated with the professional activity of the employee is also increasing. Let's first look at what an accident at work is. An accident at work is an event as a result of which an employee died or was injured in the performance of work duties or work in the interests of the employer. Depending on the criterion used, the following types of accidents can be distinguished: by the number of victims - individual and group (when 2 or more people received damage to their health); according to the main types of incidents that led to an accident - road accidents, electric shock, exposure to extreme temperatures, physical overload, etc. Accidents that have the following features are subject to investigation: first, the victim is an employee or other person participating in the employer's production activities, including one who is subject to compulsory social insurance against industrial accidents and occupational diseases; the second event that occurred is indicated in the list of events that qualify as accidents.

As already noted, an accident at work can occur not only with an employee of the organization, but also with another person acting on behalf of or in the interests of the employer. That is, for example, citizens who are serving sentences under a court sentence, while working in production, may suffer; persons under a contract and assignments performing work under civil law contracts; citizens participating in the liquidation of natural and man-made emergencies; foreign citizens working for hire, unless otherwise provided by a special international agreement; military personnel, including those undergoing alternative service, sent to enterprises to perform construction, agricultural and other work not related to military service; students and pupils during the internship at the enterprise.

Investigation and accounting of accidents at work is carried out in accordance with the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the "Regulations on the investigation and accounting of accidents and other injuries to the health of workers at work", approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 06.06.1997. for number 286.

Consider what kind of accidents an employer should investigate. According to paragraph 2 of the "Regulations on Investigation and Recording of Accidents and Other Injuries to the Health of Employees at Work" The following incidents are recognized as accidents at work: injuries, poisoning, heat strokes, explosions, accidents, destruction of buildings, structures and structures, burns, frostbite, drowning, electric shock and lightning, damage resulting from contact with animals, insects and

reptiles, terrorist acts, as well as other damage to health in natural disasters (earthquakes, landslides, floods, hurricanes, etc.) that occurred during the performance of work duties (as well as on business trips) on the territory enterprises and beyond; when performing any actions in the interests of the enterprise, although without the instructions of the employer, in the performance of their functional duties, as well as in order to prevent accidents, death of people and preserve the property of the enterprise; in case of a traffic accident, on railway, air, sea and river transport, electric transport - while the employee is on a business trip or while he is performing his functional duties; on the way to work or from work on transport intended for the transport of people, specially allocated by order of the employer for the transport of employees from home to work and / or from work home, as well as on transport of a third-party organization, provided for these purposes according to the contract (application); during working hours on personal transport in the presence of a written order of the employer on permission to use it for business trips; during working hours on transport or along the route on foot with an employee moving to fulfill the task of the employer, as well as with an employee whose activities are related to movement between service facilities; when conducting subbotnik (Sunday), civil protection exercises, competitions of voluntary fire protection, when engaging in agricultural work, providing patronage assistance by the enterprise on the written order of the employer, regardless of the location of the events or the performance of work; during working hours, the infliction of bodily harm by another person in the performance of labor duties - on the basis of information from the internal affairs bodies; on a vehicle, on the territory of a rotational camp or rental premises with an employee who is on shift rest (guide, refrigerator crew employee, shift driver, employees of sea and river vessels, as well as with workers on a rotational expedition basis, etc.).

Cases of natural death, suicide, deliberate damage to one's health by the victim, as well as injuries received by the victim in the course of committing a crime (according to the conclusion of a forensic medical examination or certificate from the investigating authorities) are not subject to investigation and accounting.

The accident needs to be investigated. To establish whether an accident is related to production or not, only the commission is entitled during the investigation, which must be organized by the employer. By order of the employer, a special commission is created in the organization where the incident occurred. It includes representatives of the employer and the trade union committee or other representative body of employees. She will have to study all the circumstances of the incident and draw up an act based on the results.

If an accident occurs that results in serious bodily injury or death, then the composition of the commission is expanded and a special investigation is carried out.

What does the commission do? The commission must examine the scene, interview eyewitnesses of the accident, the management of the organization, and the victim, if possible. If necessary, the commission can take a photo or video filming, read similar records provided by the organization, draw up a plan or diagram of the incident. Also, the commission has the right to invite experts (for calculations, measurements, etc.). And of course, members of the commission should study the documents related to labor protection. For example, extracts from the registers of occupational safety briefings, documents evidencing the issuance of PPE to the victim, etc. The results of the investigation of an accident recognized as related to production are documented in an act in the form H-1. Accounting for an accident is carried out by the organization where it occurred. To do this, an entry is made in the register of accidents at work. Most of the information reflected in the journal is transferred to it from the act following the results of the investigation.

The procedure for investigating and recording accidents at work is very relevant and timely due to the fact that, firstly, workers represent the largest group of participants in social relations related to the main type of human activity - labor, and secondly, it has been proved that the proper level of labor protection and safety is directly related to the level of labor productivity and its efficiency. In addition, today the problem of industrial injuries is the most acute, in reducing the level of which, first of all, the state and employers are interested. This is the first aspect of the relevance of the chosen topic. The second aspect of relevance is that almost every organization was brought to administrative responsibility, albeit for minor violations of labor protection requirements.

So why do accidents happen at work? In most cases, it is the fault of the victim himself, who, as a rule, deliberately violates instructions and rules on labor protection, labor and production discipline. Every accident is the result of the interaction of several causes. It is important to establish the reasons in full, so that each employee knows that an accident is a natural result of a violation of labor and production discipline, non-compliance with instructions and labor safety rules, so that he hopes for himself, for his own attitude to his own safety.

The main task in the fight against industrial injuries is the prevention of accidents at work and the preservation of the life and health of workers. One of the ways to solve this problem is the system of legal regulation of labor protection, provided with an effective mechanism for fulfilling the established requirements. Ideally, an occupational accident prevention system consists of two parts. Firstly, this is the regulatory consolidation of provisions aimed at preventing accidents at work by reducing the impact of hazardous production factors on workers. In this aspect, the prevention of industrial accidents is represented by the institute of labor protection, which includes legal measures and means to ensure the safety of life and health of workers in the course of their work. Secondly, it is bringing to justice those responsible for the accident. This is necessary because many employers do not create safe working conditions in the workplace. Gross violations of discipline, safety rules, illegal actions of persons organizing the production of work are allowed.

Based on the foregoing, we can conclude that accidents at work have always been, are and will be. But through strict discipline, they can be minimized, since in the first place it depends on the employer and the employee himself.

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